

PEDAGOGICAL ORIENTATION USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS

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The education system of Uzbekistan in recent decades has been actively developing in line with innovative technologies introduced at all levels of the educational process. The professional activity of teachers of higher education was no exception, the innovative development of which is a priority direction today [1]. The need for essential and technological improvement of the practical activities of educators is due not only to changes in social life, but also to transformations in the thinking of modern man.

Responding to changing priorities and involving a significant arsenal of phenomena and facts of the outside world in their professional activities is an essential quality of a modern teacher. The elimination of factors that limit the freedom of action of a specialist creates the conditions required by modernity for his professional growth: a willingness to respond to the challenges and proposals of the labor market, to critically perceive and evaluate one's own and others' actions, to identify tendentious, biased points of view and to avoid biased opinions and judgments, to take independent decisions and take responsibility for them.

Despite the need for innovation, most educational institutions do not seek to innovate in the process of both school and university education. A significant number of leaders and workers in this area are not familiar with the promising models of education and upbringing that have become part of the wide pedagogical practice of different countries. The low level of awareness of the achievements being introduced in this area and, at the same time, the weak level of individual pedagogical competencies is, as a rule, the result of the lack of an innovative environment in educational institutions. Consequently, the path of "investing" in scientific and educational innovations requires new principles of training and the application of innovative technologies not so much in educational activities as in the subsequent professional skills of future specialists. In the matter of forming the student's personality, the teacher should abandon clichés and stereotypes, creating "new standards of personal-creative, individually directed activity" [3].

The modern dictionary of pedagogy is an innovation in pedagogical activity, changes in the content and technology of training and education, with the aim of increasing their effectiveness" [2]. This definition, as we see, determines the key

to updating the essence of educational and educational acts and ways to modernize it. An important component is the purpose of such transformations: along with the indicated efficiency, “new in pedagogy” is correlated with such categories as relevant, advanced, useful, progressive [1]. We also insist on the importance of goal-setting in the course of innovative transformations, as we are confident that any system of existing relations (and the education system is no exception) needs to be reformed only if it needs to be improved. Therefore, “not only ideas, approaches, methods, technologies” and their previously unused combinations are recognized as valuable [2], but also “a set of elements that carry a progressive beginning, allow in changing conditions and situations effectively solve the problems of upbringing and education. A number of scientists consider the modernization of pedagogical activity broadly, namely, in close connection of innovations "to transformations, changes in the way of activity, the style of thinking that is associated with these innovations"[1].

According to the recognized theorists V. Slastenin and others, the innovative “reset” in the work of a teacher is due to the demands of modern society and the consequences provoked by them: socio-economic restructuring requires a decisive update of educational policy: methodology, principles for creating pedagogical innovations and their testing, organization of the educational process in educational institutions of various types; the humanization of education entails a revision of the content, volume, composition of academic disciplines, as well as approaches to learning; a different nature of the development of pedagogical innovations suggests a departure from the strict regulation of the educational process in favor of the teacher's free choice of both teaching aids (programs, manuals, etc.) and professional approaches to teaching with the priority of the multidirectional research nature of education; market relations dictate the need for new types of state and non-state educational institutions and imply their real competition [3].

So, the phasing of the innovation process is represented by successive stages: discovery - the embodiment of innovation in a material or spiritual product - the refinement of innovation in the course of its application - the introduction of innovation in new areas - the loss of novelty due to the advantage of innovation in a particular area - the emergence of an alternative that is more effective regarding this innovation. The full cycle of innovations consists of five stages: from the start, through rapid growth, maturity and saturation to the finish line (crisis). The indicated linear dynamics of the innovation process is a somewhat simplified scheme for the development of pedagogical activity. In the

pedagogical literature, two types of innovations in the field of education are distinguished:

1) processes that occur largely spontaneously, that is, they are not regulated by need, but generate it themselves without understanding all the circumstances, ways and forms of innovation

2) innovations that are the result of a meaningful, purposeful scientific thought. If the first type is carried out on an empirical basis, under the influence, in the overwhelming majority of cases, of situational requirements, then the second type is the result of complete scientific justifications and calculations.

The most important issue is the activity of the teacher in the development of innovations. Here it is significant that educators understand the meaning of introducing certain innovations, that is, the presence of personal innovative potential. The parameters of the innovative potential of the teacher's personality are the creative ability to develop fresh ideas; openness to new knowledge and tolerance for judgments different from one's own; readiness to improve the level of professional competencies; significant innovative consciousness [2].

The true implementation of innovative activity is based on the ability of an educator to build a concept of pedagogical innovation: to predict, develop an experiment plan, analyze actions, implement innovative programs for promotion and implementation, correction and reflection of the results of innovative actions. A special place is given to diagnostics, because the entire cycle of pedagogical innovations should be consistent with real pedagogical experience. It is the diagnostic approach that makes it possible to get an idea of the requests and needs of teachers, to identify the strengths and reveal the weaknesses of their activities. Thus, the technology of purposeful work on the formation of a professional culture of a teacher is contained in the diagnostic technique of N. S. Kovaleva [2]. Success in the course of its application is guaranteed by a clear focus on innovative creativity and initiative of educators, a significant quality and condition for the successful implementation of their professional competencies is the ability to find non-standard solutions, experiment, resolve problematic situations in the course of introducing innovations, and eliminate innovative barriers.

An analysis of the positions of scientists and researchers on the issue under study allowed us to interpret the innovative orientation of pedagogical activity as a creative process of teaching and its practice-oriented result. This category is realizable only if the subjects of the educational system have a certain degree of freedom of action, the desire to express themselves in the profession, to

creatively apply their abilities. Difficulties along the way open up the prospect of solving them on our own. Consequently, effective innovative activity can only be carried out by a trained teacher with significant intellectual and creative potential, a person striving for self-development in the profession, personally interested in mastering innovations and their further creative implementation.

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